

Effect of Use Audio Visual Media and Motivation on Student Learning Outcomes in Arts and Culture Subjects at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci

Yundari Afrinata^{1*}, Irwan²

Postgraduate of Art Institute Padang Panjang Indonesian

Corresponding Author: Yundari Afrinata yundariafrinata02@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the use of audio visual media and motivation on student learning outcomes in arts and culture subjects at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci. This research aims to find out whether there is an influence from the use of audio-visual media (X1) and motivation (X2) on learning outcomes (Y). This research approach is quantitative with quasi experimental method. Data collection techniques using observation techniques, interviews, questionnaires (questionnaires), tests and documentation. The sample in this study were 33 students in the experimental class using audio-visual media and 33 students in the control class. In this study using multiple linear regression analysis and F test and T test. This study concluded that the results of testing the t test or hypothesis 1 of 4.415 means $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($4.415 > 0.355$) and significance ($0.000 < 0.05$) then it can be concluded that there is an influence of the use of audio-visual media (X1) on learning outcomes (Y). Hypothesis 2 testing the t test of ($4.906 > 0.355$) and significance ($0.000 < 0.05$) so there is an effect of motivation (X2) on student learning outcomes (Y). Hypothesis 3 testing the t test of ($2.798 > 0.355$) and significance ($0.000 < 0.05$) so there is an influence of audio-visual media (X1) and motivation (X2) simultaneously on student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci.

INTRODUCTION

The learning process cannot be separated from the learning process and outcomes. Learning is a complex process that occurs in every person throughout his life. The learning process occurs because of the interaction between a person and his environment (Azhar, 2008: 1). The learning process basically aims to direct students to the final goal with good results , to be able to optimize Arts and Culture lessons at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci.

According to Yulianti Tri, the learning process occurs because of the interaction between a person and their environment. The environment also has a very important role in the learning process because it is common to find natural processes between individuals, individuals and groups and groups and groups. On the other hand, students are also required to complete school assignments that have been obtained from the teaching and learning process at school. However, there is an obstacle for students in completing school assignments if the lessons they receive are difficult for students to understand, perhaps because the delivery of learning material is less interesting, monotonous, boring, so this becomes a problem for students in completing their assignments.

M ardianto in S . (2012: 186) explains that learning motivation is a process that gives enthusiasm for learning, direction and persistence of behavior , meaning that motivated behavior is behavior that is full of energy, directed and long-lasting. In Arts and Culture learning it is very important to use audio-visual media in the process. learning. Motivation is an urge from within an individual to carry out an action in a certain way in accordance with the planned Cultural Arts learning objectives.

Arts and Culture learning has so far been less relevant and less popular with students. This is due to the lack of application and utilization of technology in the Arts and Culture learning process. The use of technology in the learning process can support and assist teachers in delivering material. Arts and Culture learning that should be carried out is learning that can make students focus and be able to think logically, critically and creatively. So that the learning outcomes obtained by students reach the targets that have been set. The instrument used to measure the learning outcomes of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci in the cognitive aspect is a test.

According to Sudjana Nana (2016 : 27) "Learning outcomes are the abilities that students have after receiving their learning experience". Learning in where students are only required to pay attention to the explanation of the material presented by the teacher without the involvement of students to be active in asking questions, responding to the material, interacting and expressing opinions which will influence student learning outcomes.

According to Sulastianto Harry (2010: 148) states that Arts and Culture is a skill in the activity of expressing ideas and aesthetic thoughts, including realizing abilities and imagination of views of several objects, works or atmospheres, which can present a feeling of beauty and create further human civilization. The learning process is carried out at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci which

is located on Jalan Lintas Sungai Banyak-Padang, Siulak Deras Mudik, Gunung Kerinci District, Kerinci Regency, Jambi Province.

Based on observations made at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci, audio-visual media has a big influence on student learning outcomes. Audio visual media itself has various types , one type of audio visual media is power point media , in where as technology develops and teachers' professionalism demands, they are expected to be able to master computer-based technology.

This computer technology can be used to create audio-visual media using Power Point. This power point media can present various elements into one complete presentation and attract students' interest. Apart from that, this power point media does not need to cost a lot because internet access is enough to collect materials and materials that will be used .

The reality that occurs in the field is that teachers still do not maximize the existence of the program SPSS . In fact, on average, every teacher has a computer or laptop, even at school computer facilities are provided which always have at least 1 unit of access to the internet. Thus, there should be no reason to use audio-visual media with power points. Even though many students' learning outcomes in Arts and Culture learning have not yet reached the KKM, they can be improved through the use of audio-visual media in the form of power points.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

M ardianto in S . (2012: 186) explains that learning motivation is a process that gives enthusiasm for learning, direction and persistence of behavior , meaning that motivated behavior is behavior that is full of energy, directed and long-lasting. In Arts and Culture learning it is very important to use audio-visual media in the process. learning. Motivation is an urge from within an individual to carry out an action in a certain way in accordance with the planned Cultural Arts learning objectives.

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METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative research, this type of research is quasi-experimental research which uses an experimental method in the form of a factorial design. Experimental research is research that aims to obtain information that can be obtained from experiments based on treatment. Trying to research how much influence the use of audio-visual media has on students' motivation and learning outcomes in Arts and Culture subjects at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci, this research used two classes, namely the experimental class and the control class.

The population in this study were all class VIII students consisting of 2 classes with a total of 66 students. Meanwhile, the samples taken in this research were class VIIIA as the experimental class and class VIIIB as the control class. The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population (Sugiyono, 2015 : 56). The samples from this research were taken from two classes which were used as the experimental class and the control class. In this study, samples were taken using the normality test with *Liliefors* because the entire population will be sampled by the researcher.

The research procedure was carried out in an effort to provide a comprehensive overview of the series of research that will be carried out. First, researchers must develop systematic research stages in order to obtain systematic research results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First research reveal that there is an influence of Audio Visual Media on Student Learning Outcomes, as in the picture above, students learn using conventional media, one of which is textbooks. Here the teacher explains the material to students still guided by the RPP and teacher and student handbook. Thus, students do not understand the material presented by the teacher in class, so that when the teacher gives practical assignments to students, students feel overwhelmed to make them because they do not fully understand the material. Therefore, the learning objectives are not achieved well. With the learning delivered by the teacher to the students, the researcher invited teachers to use audio-visual media when learning Arts and Culture.

Teachers are very interested in trying to use audio-visual media when teaching arts and culture to students. Because before researchers conducted research at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci regarding audio-visual media, teachers usually only used conventional media when learning Arts and Culture, except for studying science they used audio-visual media in Labor. After that, the teacher practices directly in the teaching class using audio-visual media.

It turns out that students are more focused on paying attention to the teacher explaining and looking at the material presented in Power Point (PPT).

After the teacher delivers the material, the teacher gives practical assignments to the students and the students are enthusiastic about doing them, thus, the learning objectives are achieved well. Students also understand learning better by using audio-visual media.

This can improve learning outcomes, from research conducted at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci shows that there is an influence of the use of Audio Visual Media on student learning outcomes, this is proven by the results of researchers using multiple linear regression to determine whether there is an influence of Audio Visual Media on Student Learning Outcomes, on the basis of decision making if it is significant is greater than 0.05 ($\text{Sign} > 0.05$) then there is no influence and vice versa if the significant value is smaller than 0.05 ($\text{sign} < 0.05$) then there is a significant influence. In this study, the value obtained using *multiple linear regression* which had previously passed the normality test, homogeneity test, multicollinearity test, obtained a significant value of 0.000, which means it is smaller than 0.05, namely ($0.000 < 0.05$), this means that there is an influence of Audio Visual Media (X) on Student Learning Outcomes (Y).

In *Multiple Linear Regression* There is also a B coefficient or also called the regression direction and states the average change in the Audio Visual Media Variable (X) for each change in the Audio Visual Media variable by one unit. This change is an increase if B is positive and a decrease if B is negative. The calculation results if $F_{count} > F_{table}$ with a significance of less than 0.05 then there is an influence of Variable X on variable Y.

Thus, the higher the level of influence of Audio Visual Media, the higher the level of learning success of students at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci . So, it is clear that the use of learning media, one of which is audio-visual media, can improve student learning outcomes and also generate a sense of joy in students. This is in line with Azhar Arsyad's opinion, which says that learning media brings and arouses students' feelings of joy and happiness and renews their enthusiasm , strengthens knowledge in the minds of students and bring learning to life. The use of learning media is necessary as well as new media to make learning more interesting for students in achieving effective learning outcomes.

Learning with audio visual media is a learning process using collaboration between the senses of sight and hearing and practical values are inserted in the learning plan in both initial, core and closing activities. The learning process uses a collaboration between the senses of sight and the sense of hearing, which is realized through an animated video about batik making. As stated in the RPP, it is included in this activity.

The learning process begins with a pre-test and continues with group division into 3 groups, each group consisting of 7 students appointed by the teacher. Next is the student's activity by watching the video given by the teacher. Only a small number of students were enthusiastic about watching the video played by the teacher. This is similar to the process of providing material, only a small number of students pay close attention to the explanation of the material given by the teacher. Other students were seen having fun chatting with their table mates, reading other textbooks, and some were even sleepy. Even when the teacher asked students to provide conclusions about the content

of the video they were watching, students felt embarrassed and were reluctant to express their opinions.

Based on the explanation above regarding the results of the research at the initial meeting, the researcher felt that the research should be continued at the second meeting because it was felt that he had not succeeded in implementing audio visual media in Arts and Culture learning. Apart from that, student motivation still needs to be reminded. However, the majority of students look happy and enthusiastic when learning Arts and Culture using audio-visual media.

At the planning stage for the second meeting, the researcher prepared a learning implementation plan (RPP), a video about batik making, an observation sheet of teacher, student and learning activities and a questionnaire. The researcher established with a collaborating teacher as well as an observer, the actions to be carried out reflecting the results of the reflection that had been discussed previously. Apart from that, a discussion was held regarding the initial pre-test and final test questions (post-test). Based on the results of the reflection at the first meeting, students will be divided into 3 groups, each group consisting of 7 students. However, at the second meeting, group division will be directed towards the group they control. Each group will be led by one student who acts as group leader. With this group discussion, it is hoped that it can increase student motivation and grow a sense of social responsibility in students.

The expected results at this second meeting are that students will become more interested in Arts and Culture lessons and there will be an increase in the percentage of students in motivational activities for learning Arts and Culture from the previous meeting.

At this meeting the researcher, who acted as a subject teacher, gave a game in the form of *an ice breaker* in the form of a quiz on the previous material at the beginning of the lesson. The benefit was to increase students' motivation in learning Arts and Culture.

At this meeting, there were slightly fewer students who did not pay attention to the video given by the teacher. Almost all students watched the video about batik and paid serious attention to the teacher's explanation. They look enthusiastic and enjoy the learning process.

It is easier for students to understand learning Arts and Culture by using audio-visual media compared to conventional media or just using textbooks, because studying Arts and Culture students are usually given practical assignments, so if they don't use audio-visual media it becomes difficult for students to understand and the teacher will be overwhelmed. to explain the material to students because it does not use audio-visual media.

When the researcher explained the learning media with batik material, almost all students paid attention to the material presented. After the material was presented, the teacher asked the students questions about batik, the students enthusiastically answered these questions. This means that students already understand the material that has been presented. Before the lesson ends, students are given the opportunity to ask questions about material they

do not understand and after that the lesson ends with students filling out a questionnaire with 25 post-test questions.

In the final stage, namely analysis and reflection, where the researcher together with the subject teacher who serves as a collaboration and observer and observer analyze and evaluate the learning process at the second meeting, whether the actions that have been given are in accordance with the research concept that has been planned or not. Then the results of the second research meeting were compared with the indicators of success.

The learning process using audio-visual media has gone well because all students have followed the learning well. Both in watching the video displayed and in expressing conclusions (opinions) and difficulties in progress as well as expressing questions to the teacher, even though they have not yet reached perfection, the teacher is considered successful in carrying out the learning process using audio-visual media about batik. This is proven by increased learning achievement and student motivation. So the researcher feels that his actions have succeeded in achieving the indicators of success.

From the results of the questionnaire analysis, it was proven that the average student response in the experimental class was 75%, meaning that almost all students agreed that learning using audio-visual media could improve the learning outcomes and motivation of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci.

Based on the results of *Multiple Linear Regression* As has been explained, the researcher also used *the Paired Samples t-Test* to find out whether there were differences in the test of two paired samples. In the third finding, after carrying out *the Paired t-Test*, the researcher revealed that there were differences between the experimental class and the control class in terms of student learning outcomes.

There is a difference in the average score of the Student Motivation variable questionnaire for the Experimental Class *Pretest* and the Experimental Class *Posttest* . Thus it can be concluded that the application of Audio Visual Media and motivation in Arts and Culture subjects can improve student learning outcomes (Y).

Arts and Culture learning by applying Audio Visual Media is more effective than conventional learning. This is because using Audio Visual Media in the form of videos can arouse students' interest in learning.

The students looked enthusiastic in learning, the students paid close attention to the video, after watching the video the students immediately discussed, asked questions with their friends next to them and there were also those who directly asked the teacher without having to be provoked first. Students also immediately put into practice the lessons they have learned according to what they see in the video, students are also able to answer questions from the teacher and provide feedback, this is because students' comprehension is faster when learning contains both elements, namely the sound element and also contains picture elements. can be seen.

Students can also be motivated by watching the batik making videos that are presented and they will also be inspired to want to practice making batik.

Because they already understand the steps for making batik that the teacher presents in power point when explaining the learning material. Apart from being able to increase interest in studying Arts and Culture , using Audio Visual Media can also improve learning outcomes for Arts and Culture.

So it can be concluded that audio visual media and motivation simultaneously influence the learning outcomes of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There is an influence of Audio Visual Media (X1) on Student Learning Outcomes (Y) of SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci. This can be seen from the *t test* showing that the significance is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus it can be concluded that Audio Visual Media (X) influences Student Learning Outcomes (Y). A positive calculated *t* value means that it has a positive effect, namely if Audio Visual Learning Media continues to be used then Student Learning Outcomes will increase. There is a significant influence between Motivation (X2) on Student Learning Outcomes (Y) at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci. This can be seen from the test showing that the significance is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus it can be concluded that Motivation (X2) influences Student Learning Outcomes (Y2). A positive calculated *t* value means that it has a positive effect, namely if Audio Visual Learning Media continues to be used then Student Results will increase.

There is a significant difference between Audio Visual Media (X1), Motivation (X2) on Student Learning Outcomes (Y) at SMP Negeri 17 Kerinci. Based on the *Paired t-Test*, the researcher revealed that there were differences between the *experimental class* and the *control class* in terms of student learning outcomes. Based on the output of Pair 1 and Pair 2 on Variable Y or Student Learning Motivation , a *Sig (2 tailed)* value of $0.000 < 0.05$ is obtained , so it can be concluded that there is a difference in the average student learning outcomes for the *Experimental class Pretest* and the *Experimental class Posttest* . Thus, it can be seen that the application of Audio Visual Media in Arts and Culture subjects can improve student learning outcomes (Y).

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